

LEADER

Learnings for European
Autonomy to Deliver Europe's
Rail in 2030

Powering Europe's rail future

From supply risks to strategic
autonomy: securing materials
and technologies behind
rail innovation

**A chain is only as strong
as its weakest link.**

***'Risk management comes at a price,
but that cost of strategic autonomy, of sovereignty can also be shared.'***

Mark Carney, Prime Minister of Canada, Special address at World Economic Forum 2026

***'Countries are not rich in proportion to their natural resources.
Countries are rich whose governments have policies which
encourage the essential creativity, initiative and enterprise of man
and recognize his desire to do better for his family.'***

Margaret Thatcher, British Prime Minister, 1979-1990

'The Middle East has oil, China has rare earths.'

*Deng Xiaoping, Chinese statesman, revolutionary, and political theorist who served as the
paramount leader of the People's Republic of China, from 1978-1989*

Figure 1 | A battery pack for rail traction exposed at InnoTrans Fair, Berlin 2024 (Photo: GKZ)

Executive Summary

PROBLEM

The European Rail value chain is undergoing a profound transformation “to deliver, via an integrated system approach, a high capacity, flexible, multi-modal, sustainable and reliable integrated European railway network by eliminating barriers to interoperability and providing solutions for full integration, for European citizens and cargo”, to “make rail the everyday mobility”¹.

Technological innovation tends to introduce new material dependencies, reinforcing long-term pressure on supply systems. For this reason, the deployment of multiple Rail innovations in parallel, whilst aimed at delivering a coordinated and time-bound transformation, is significantly increasing not only the complexity and interdependencies of the Rail value chain, but also systemic supply chain risks, in a context marked by heightened geopolitical tensions, strong supply dependencies, growing constraints on access to critical raw materials and components, and competition between industrial sectors for the same pool of materials.

So, while the Rail transformation in which the European Commission and European industries are investing jointly is essential to enhance performance, sustainability and competitiveness in the EU, it also amplifies existing vulnerabilities and generates new ones as the Rail innovations under development are critical material-intensive technologies.

WHY IT MATTERS (1)

Like in other EU industrial sectors, Rail supplies are impacted by the too many EU dependencies in Critical Raw Materials (CRM) and components and by the continuous, multiple disruptions due to the permacrisis status in which we are living. Despite ‘we’re not alone in this’, there is the need for an *ad hoc* attention to increase the autonomy of supplies for the European Rail sector and its innovations because without a fully functioning and modern railway system, Europe cannot fully deliver on several of its ambitions—not only in transport, such as the Single European Railway Area and the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T), but also on broader structural objectives, including achieving a climate-neutral continent and translating the Single Market’s principles of free movement of people and goods into operational reality.

WHY IT MATTERS (2)

While addressing the challenge of future Rail supplies, the clear identification of the multiple needs of the EU Raw Materials value chain has been made. Addressing these will help not only the Railway sector to become more resilient and deliver its EU-level mission, but also the other industrial sectors affected by similar supply risks. In fact, the European Raw Materials value chain—from exploration and extraction to processing, recycling and substitution—has become both a strategic industrial sector in its own and a critical enabler for multiple key EU industries.

WHAT SHOULD BE DONE

Strengthening the resilience, sustainability, and strategic autonomy of the European Rail value chain as well as reinforcing the European Raw Materials value chain requires a systemic, coordinated and forward-looking policy approach, combining industrial, regulatory, financial and technological measures.

A wide set of recommendations derived from the research and lessons learnt within the “LEADER 2030” project have been identified. In this Policy Brief they are structured into seven cross-cutting thematic priorities, reflecting the key levers for action at EU, national, regional and industry levels.

¹ Europe’s Rail Joint Undertaking (2022), Multi-Annual Work Programme, p. 10.

Problem, context, and diagnosis

PROBLEM

The Rail sector in Europe contributes approximately €250 billion to the GDP of EU countries, representing around 1.4% of total EU GDP, and supports 3.1 million jobs². It remains a global leader in rail solutions, with a highly innovative and export-oriented industry. However, this leadership is increasingly challenged by rising global competition and growing trade barriers, as well as by structural dependencies on external supplies and recurring disruptions, making it essential to actively preserve and strengthen the sector resilience, innovation capacity, competitive position, and contribution to Europe's growth.

European Rail industries' reliance on supplies from outside the EU already accounted for around one quarter of needs in 2014³. The European Rail value chain is increasingly exposed to systemic and structural supply dependencies and disruptions, which risk undermining the timely deployment of rail innovations, the completion of the Single European Railway Area, of the TEN-T corridors, the realization of a net-zero continent, and the operational realization of the EU Single Market.

Evidence from the LEADER 2030 studies highlights both the scale and persistence of these disruptions and the increasing dependencies the rail innovations will be subject to.

When it comes to **disruptions**, most companies of the European Rail value chain (58%) reported having experienced supply disruptions in recent years, **affecting both standard/state-of-the-art and innovative supplies**, but only a smaller part (23,8%) of companies can be considered genuinely disruption-free. These disruptions are predominantly supply-driven (87%), but are also strongly linked to economic and financial pressures (71%, including skyrocketing materials prices, energy prices, freight costs), to logistics (delays) and manufacturing-related disruptions (need to transition to advanced technologies and new modalities driven by evolving customer requirements), as well as to demand-driven disruptions (35%) which represent a further important alert in view of upcoming innovation-driven transformations in the rail sector. The main reason for such disruptions is in fact *change in the products/services requested*, which also highlights the risk of obsolescence management.

The most affected inputs span the entire value chain, as shown in the next Figure, including raw materials (such as iron, aluminium, copper and rare earth elements), processed materials (including alloys and plastics), and components, with semiconductors and electronic systems being particularly critical.

² Oxford Economics (2024), [The Economic Footprint of Railway Transport in Europe](#), p. iv.

³ European Commission (2019), [Final Report: Study on the Competitiveness of the European Rail Supply Industry](#).

Figure 2 | Disruption pathways in the European Rail Value chain (2018-2023) surveyed in “LEADER 2030”

These disruptions are further exacerbated by:

- limited substitution options, especially for **critical raw materials and advanced electronics, but not only**: so-called “**ordinary**” inputs, such as basic components or intermediate products, can also become critical bottlenecks when their supply is disrupted
- a persistent **cost gap of around 30% for EU-based alternatives, when existing**;
- **low levels of circularity** within industrial value chains;
- and continued reliance on **global supply networks** exposed to geopolitical and logistical shocks.

At the same time, the resilience strategies adopted nowadays by most companies—such as stockpiling and supplier diversification—are cost-intensive and difficult to sustain over time, particularly in a context increasingly characterised by continuous and overlapping crises (“**permacrisis**”). This raises fundamental questions about the long-term sustainability of current approaches to supply chain risk management.

Today, **delivering the EU's rail innovation agenda** is increasing the demand for raw materials and components whose huge majority is sourced in non-EU countries. This at the same time **deepens supply dependencies and disruptions risks** also affecting other European industrial ecosystems, but while these are already well recognised at both policy and industry level in some sectors (e.g. Clean Energy Technologies, Automotive, Defence and Aerospace, Electronics), they remain **comparatively less acknowledged within and across the Rail value chain**.

As a result, the Rail sector is increasingly exposed to systemic and structural supply chain threats, which may undermine the timely deployment of rail innovations, the resilience of this critical industrial sector for the EU, and, ultimately, the achievement of key EU objectives.

The “LEADER 2030” project—funded by the Europe's Rail public-private partnership (PPP) on rail research and innovation established under the Horizon Europe programme (2021-2027)—aimed to identify and better detail the specific risks emerging from the development of the specific innovations the EU is supporting through the Europe's Rail programme with 1,2 billion euros of public-private investments. The “LEADER 2030” strategic goal was to **raise alerts well ahead of industrial production of such innovations**—namely of the **Flagship Projects (FPs)**—in order to **reconfigure or to deploy the risk mitigation actions** needed to regularly produce:

- **Network Management & Mobility (FP1 - MOTIONAL)**: Advanced traffic management systems, real-time data analytics, and digital platforms enhance operational efficiency and network capacity.
- **Digital & Autonomous Train Operations (FP2 - R2DATO)**: Automatic Train Operation (ATO), AI-driven control systems, and advanced sensor technologies improve safety, reliability, and cost efficiency.
- **Intelligent & Integrated Asset Management (FP3 - IAM4RAIL)**: Predictive maintenance systems, Digital-Twins, and IoT-based sensors optimize asset lifecycle and reduce maintenance costs.
- **Sustainable & Green Rail Systems (FP4 - RAIL4EARTH)**: Energy-efficient propulsion, sustainable materials, and emissions reduction technologies drive sustainability efforts.
- **Competitive Digital Green Rail Freight (FP5 - TRANS4M-R)**: Digital Automatic Couplers (DAC), intelligent freight systems, and smart grid integration enhance efficiency and sustainability for seamless Rail freight.
- **Regional & Capillary Rail Services (FP6 - FUTURE)**: Modular vehicles, cost-efficient infrastructure, and customer-centric digital services improve accessibility and affordability.
- **New Approaches for Guided Transport (FP7 - Pods4Rail)**: Automated multimodal transport systems and ultra-high-speed trains introduce innovative mobility solutions.

CONTEXT

Drivers of raw materials demand

The demand for raw materials, especially CRM (i.e. those with high economic importance and exposure to high supply risk, often caused by a high concentration of supply from a few third countries), is growing rapidly at both global and European levels, driven primarily by the twin green and digital transitions, but increasingly also by Aerospace and Defence sectors. In terms of global Net-Zero targets, the deployment of clean energy technologies alone is expected to significantly increase CRM demand by 2030, while electrification, digitalisation, and automation across sectors—including transport and rail—are intensifying the need for Strategic Raw Materials (SRM, i.e. those that score among the highest in terms of strategic importance, forecasted demand growth and difficulty of increasing production) such as rare earth elements, and semiconductor-related metals like silicon, germanium and gallium. For instance, EU’s demand for rare earths is expected to increase sixfold by 2030 and sevenfold by 2050, while that for semiconductor-related metals will at least double by 2030.

In the Rail sector, the transition towards electrified, automated, and digital systems further amplifies demand. The replacement of legacy technologies with advanced systems—such as digital signalling, AI-based monitoring, and electrified propulsion—requires a broader and more complex set of materials. At the same time, multiple industrial sectors, including automotive, energy, defence, and electronics, compete for the same pool of CRM, intensifying pressure on global supply chains. Additional demand drivers include macroeconomic trends such as population growth and rising living standards, as well as the intrinsic characteristics of material systems. Many CRM are by-products of metallurgical refining, which is an energy intensive process, meaning their supply from European domestic resources depends on competitive energy prices. Furthermore, technological innovation tends to introduce new material dependencies rather than reducing overall demand, reinforcing long-term pressure on supply systems. And: In a multipolar world, raw materials have long since become a tool of geostrategic policy, as evidenced not only by the dramatic rise in export restrictions imposed by countries such as China—a trend that is by no means a recent development. This weaponizing of CRM is driving up the criticality of the CRM supply chain due to increasing strategic stockpiling.

Figure 3 | Number of exported raw material products subject to at least one export restriction measure for reasons of competition policy and geopolitics (OECD⁴)

⁴ OECD (2025), [Inventory of Export Restrictions on Industrial Raw Materials 2025](#).

Raw materials outlook

The global outlook for raw materials availability suggests that physical scarcity is not always the primary constraint; rather, supply stability and concentration represent the main risks. While some materials—such as magnesium—are geologically abundant, their extraction (and critical know-how to process and refine) is highly concentrated in a limited number of countries, notably China, which creates systemic vulnerabilities in global supply chains. In general, both, supply and demand are expected to grow over the coming decades. However, short-term shortages remain likely due to external factors such as energy constraints, environmental regulations, and geopolitical disruptions. Even where current projects appear sufficient to meet demand in the medium term, additional capacity will be required in the 2030s under high-demand scenarios. Structural issues such as chronic underinvestment in mining, high market concentration, and dependence on a limited number of regions further reduce the resilience of supply systems and delay recovery after disruptions.

In the European context, the situation is more critical due to structural dependencies and the cumulative effects of economic and environmental policy developments at both EU and national/regional level. The EU consumes approximately one quarter of global critical raw materials but produces only a small fraction domestically, resulting in heavy reliance on imports for many materials. A combination of regulatory complexity and associated cumulative burden, the prioritisation of climate objectives, high energy costs, lengthy permitting procedures, evolving societal acceptance, and the current design of the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities has contributed to limiting the EU's ability to achieve the raw materials sovereignty targets set for 2020 under the European Innovation Partnership launched in 2012. Looking ahead, there remain significant uncertainties as to whether the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), which entered into force in 2024, will be sufficient on its own to deliver a structural turnaround by 2030.

Looking towards 2030, our conclusion is that full autonomy in raw materials supply appears unlikely.

The European Rail sector is therefore expected to continue relying on global sourcing strategies, strategic partnerships with mind-liked countries, and backward-integration of Rail OEMs as well as a strategic increase of off-take agreements to secure critical inputs.

In this context, the **EU's economic partnerships** will play an increasingly important role. The rivalry between the US and China is forcing the EU to take greater responsibility and forge new alliances. Canadian Prime Minister Mark Carney called for middle powers, such as his own, to work together to build a more cooperative, resilient world in his speech at the World Economic Forum in Davos in January this year. A trend towards the erosion of democracy within the international community stands in the way of a path based on the Enlightenment. The Economist Intelligence Unit's "Democracy Index Map" paints a clear picture for 2024 compared with previous years: democratic states are on the decline. Countries rich in natural resources, in particular, are increasingly being classified as hybrid regimes or authoritarian regimes.

Figure 4 | Democracy Index 2024, global map by regime type (EUI⁵)

Type of regime ↕	Score		Countries		Proportion of world population (%)	
	2022–2024 ↕	2006–2021 ↕	Number ↕	(%)w ↕	By types ↕	Subtotal ↕
Full democracies	9.00–10.00	9.01–10.00	25	15.0%	6.6%	45%
	8.00–8.99	8.01–9.00				
Flawed democracies	7.00–7.99	7.01–8.00	46	27.5%	38.4%	54.9%
	6.00–6.99	6.01–7.00				
Hybrid regimes	5.00–5.99	5.01–6.00	36	21.6%	15.7%	
	4.00–4.99	4.01–5.00				
Authoritarian regimes	3.00–3.99	3.01–4.00	60	35.9%	39.2%	
	2.00–2.99	2.01–3.00				
	1.00–1.99	1.01–2.00				
	0.00–0.99	0.00–1.00				

Figure 5 | Number of nations and the percentage of world population for each type of regime⁶

Limits to reduction, substitution, and circularity

Efforts to reduce dependency on CRM through substitution, recycling, and demand reduction face significant structural limitations.

Substitution, while often highlighted as a key strategy, is constrained by technological, economic, and systemic factors. Alternative materials frequently exhibit lower performance or higher costs, and the development and scaling of substitution technologies are hindered by slow innovation cycles and complex value chain dependencies. As a result, substitution can only partially mitigate supply risks and cannot fully replace critical materials in most applications.

Recycling and circularity also face important limitations. Although recycling is essential to achieving EU targets for secondary raw material supply, current performance remains insufficient. For most critical raw materials, recycling rates are below 15%, and the overall circular material use rate in the EU remains relatively low. Key barriers include inadequate collection systems, insufficient industrial capacity, technological challenges, and the continued export of recyclable

⁵ The Economist Intelligence Unit (2025), [Democracy Index 2024](#).

⁶ Wikipedia, [The Economist Democracy Index 2024](#).

waste outside the EU. Moreover, recycling processes for many critical materials are energy-intensive and subject to physical limitations, which constrain their scalability and efficiency. Meeting the CRMA target of more than 25% recycling capacity by 2030 will require substantial investment to modernise existing facilities and develop new ones, alongside parallel investments in decarbonisation driven by EU policy objectives.

Increasing cost pressures and global competition—which reduced EU industrial competitiveness—are already prioritising European industries' investments in innovation, productivity and competitiveness. The cumulative investment requirements associated with regulatory, decarbonisation and resilience objectives therefore risk placing additional strain on the sector.

This challenge is further compounded by the slower-than-expected deployment of certain low-carbon technologies—such as hydrogen—which remain below anticipated uptake levels, thereby limiting expected gains in industrial competitiveness.

At the same time, recent trends—including a decline in Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) in the EU27 and signals from key industrial indicators—suggest ongoing relocation of parts of the basic materials industry outside Europe, which cannot but raise concerns about the EU's long-term capacity to meet its raw materials objectives.

Figure 6 | Mining production rates 2000-2023: declining only in Europe (World Mining Data⁷)

Demand-side reduction is similarly constrained: CRM are fundamental to the technologies underpinning the green and digital transitions, making it difficult to significantly reduce demand without compromising strategic objectives. In many cases, efforts to reduce the use of one material lead to increased reliance on others, rather than an overall decrease in material demand. Finally, the expansion of domestic upstream production within the EU is—as in the downstream industry—limited by high energy costs, complex regulatory frameworks, limited access to finance, and societal opposition to mining activities. These factors collectively hinder the rapid development of production and processing capacities for primary and secondary raw materials, reinforcing the EU's structural dependence on external sources.

⁷ Federal Ministry Republic of Austria (2025), [World Mining Data 2025](#), p. 4.

DIAGNOSIS

Structural vulnerabilities across the Rail value chain

The LEADER 2030 analysis identified a set of systemic vulnerabilities affecting the European Rail value chain.

First, supply **risks are multi-layered and interconnected**, extending beyond raw materials to encompass components, subsystems, logistics, manufacturing and financial conditions. In such a system, even a single missing component can delay or block the delivery of entire systems, particularly in complex rail projects.

Second, the value chain is characterised by **strong dependencies and limited substitution capacity**. Many critical inputs have few or no viable alternatives, rely on non-EU suppliers, and are subject to long qualification cycles, especially in safety-critical rail applications. This results in a system that is **both rigid and slow to adapt to disruptions**.

Third, a **significant share of vulnerabilities is concentrated in lower tiers of the value chain**, particularly among SMEs. Tier-2 and Tier-3 suppliers often lack visibility, bargaining power and financial capacity, making them more exposed to disruptions while also being less able to implement resilience measures. These “hidden layers” of the value chain can therefore become critical points of failure.

Fourth, there is a **growing misalignment between policy objectives and market behaviour**. While public policies increasingly promote resilience, strategic autonomy and the diversification of supply chains, market practices continue to prioritise lowest-cost sourcing. The limited willingness of customers to accept ‘higher costs’ for ‘more secure, sustainable or European-based supplies’ constrains companies’ efforts, especially given the persistent price gap (on average around +30%) between EU and non-EU alternatives and the limited substitution potential for many critical inputs. This creates a structural contradiction whereby macroeconomic policy objectives risk being undermined by microeconomic purchasing decisions.

Fifth, the **integration of circular economy approaches remains insufficient**. Recycling, reuse and industrial symbiosis are still marginal in practice along the value chain and have not yet been fully leveraged as tools to enhance resilience. And where OEMs excelling in this field could lead the revolution, EU policymakers underestimate the impact for the ‘small dimension’ of the Railway sector compared to e.g. Automotive. As a result, dependence on primary raw materials remains high, and opportunities to stabilise supply chains through secondary materials are underexploited.

Sixth, the transition towards future rail systems introduces **new, innovation-driven vulnerabilities**. The increasing reliance on CRM, semiconductors, and digital infrastructures—combined with growing digital dependencies on non-EU providers—creates new forms of risk. LEADER 2030 **categorised** them into:

- material risks (availability, price volatility, supply concentration)
- digital dependency risks (cloud, software, platforms and firmware ecosystems)
- SME exposure risks (concentration of vulnerabilities in lower tiers).

and **aggregated** these dimensions into a “global supply risk”, complemented by the 2030 TRL/delivery risk, which indicates the maturity and likelihood of deployment of each rail innovation under development within the Europe’s Rail programme of the EU.

Overall, the analysis confirms that **supply chain risks** are not only **widespread across innovations**, but also **structurally embedded in the transformation of the rail sector**. The combination of material dependencies, digital reliance and SME exposure creates systemic vulnerabilities, where disruptions—particularly at lower tiers—can propagate across the value chain and delay the

deployment of critical rail innovations. The Figure below illustrates this, together with the likelihood that the innovations within each Europe’s Rail Flagship Project (FP) will reach the target TRL by 2030.

Figure 7 | Risk-exposure heat map of Europe’s Rail Flagship Projects

Seventh, in accessing the critical materials and components needed, the Rail innovations analysed will **have to compete with other sectors where there is both a growing market demand and strong policy pull** (Clean Technologies, Electric Vehicles, Defence, etc.):

Figure 8 | Semi-quantitative measure of material over-lap with the other, most demanding sectors based on the 10 key raw materials required by each FP (it does not pretend to forecast the exact future market shares or absolute tonnage demand)

Eight, the transformation process generates **obsolescence** and—if not managed properly throughout the Rail value chain—**transition risks**. As new technologies are deployed, legacy systems and components are phased out, potentially leading to **supplier exclusion and loss of industrial capabilities**, which further threatens the resilience of the Rail value chain because of the rapidity and scale of the transformation ignited. At the same time, delays in innovation deployment may require maintaining legacy systems longer than planned, resulting in dual supply chains and increased complexity. The Deployment groups established

Finally, there is a **significant gap between R&D and real-world supply constraints**: innovation roadmaps often underestimate supply chain risks, and the use of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) solutions does not eliminate vulnerabilities. Supply constraints are not sufficiently integrated into early design phases, highlighting the need for **“design for resilience”** approaches.

Addressing these challenges requires moving:

- from reactive to **anticipatory resilience**
- from fragmented actions to **system-level coordination**
- from cost-driven to **value-chain-driven decision-making**.

Competitive weaknesses of the Raw Materials value chain

The LEADER 2030 analysis highlights several interconnected structural problems affecting raw materials supply.

First, the **EU remains highly dependent on external suppliers and on the technological know-how of its competitors**, particularly in the field of processing and refining CRM, which cannot be easily caught up with. The best example is China's virtual monopoly on the processing of rare earths. This results often in relying on a limited number of countries for key materials. This concentration exposes supply chains to geopolitical risks and potential disruptions.

Second, supply chains are themselves inherently fragile, as recent crises have clearly demonstrated. Events such as geopolitical tensions, pandemics and logistical bottlenecks have had far-reaching impacts across industrial ecosystems, with raw materials, energy and metals accounting for a significant share of observed disruptions. While previous crises—such as the oil shocks of the 1970s or China's export restrictions in 2010—already highlighted the strategic importance of securing access to critical raw materials, the extent to which these lessons have been fully translated into long-term structural resilience remains uneven. This is particularly relevant in light of early geopolitical signals, such as the well-known statement attributed to Deng Xiaoping in the early 1990s that “the Middle East has oil, China has rare earths”, which pointed to the strategic dimension of resource control. This was more than 15 years before the EU's Raw Materials Initiative—equivalent to the full lead time of a mining project— and shows the importance of signals, sustained anticipation and long-term strategic alignment.

A third major issue is the growing imbalance between rapidly increasing demand and the limited flexibility of supply systems. Expanding mining and processing capacity requires **long lead times and significant investment**, making it difficult for supply to keep pace with accelerating demand. Investment is driven not by demand, but by the capital market and the return on investment (ROI). Ultimately, mining—and recycling too—is carried out to make money. Mining operators therefore invest in commodities that offer a **quick return on investment and high profits**. These commodities do not necessarily include all critically needed CRM. Furthermore, as shown above, some of them are by-products of downstream industries which are subject to other investment incentives.

As, shown in the next Figure, project development lead times differ by commodities but also by region. For lithium, for instance, in the EU the average development lead times based on advanced projects tend to be much longer than compared to Australia or South America.

Project development lead times: Market tightness can appear much more quickly than new projects

Note: Global average values are based on the top 35 mining projects that came online between 2010 and 2019. Source: IEA analysis based on S&P Global (2020), S&P Global (2019a) and Schodde (2017). IEA. All rights reserved.

Figure 9 | Project development lead times (IEA⁸)

Figure 10 | The share of the non-ferrous minerals in global mining shows that, apart from aluminium (Al) and copper (Cu), all other CRM do not even account for 1% of the total volume: this is explained not only for their comparatively low volumes, but also-as investments are based on margins-to their significantly worse mining cost-benefit ratio⁹

⁸ IEA (2021), [Average observed lead times from discovery to production for selected minerals, 2010-2019](#).

⁹ Based on Op. cit., Federal Ministry Republic of Austria (2025).

In addition, existing policy instruments are not yet fully effective, and particularly environmental regulations are not coherent to those aiming to push domestic supply forward.

Trade agreements, while potentially useful, are often slow to negotiate and ratify, often with little investment from industry limiting their short-term impact. Similarly, raw materials partnerships, although strategically important, are largely non-binding and face implementation challenges.

Furthermore, compared to the size of the market and the EU’s significance as a production hub in a global context, **only a few mining companies are now based in the EU**, as illustrated in the next Figure, which explains SUERF (The European Money and Finance Forum) analysis conclusions: EU investors play only a minor role in the ownership of global CRM mining companies.

	China	United States	European Union	United Kingdom	Canada	Australia	Latin America	Africa
Rare earths	73%	15%	0%	2%	0%	6%	0%	0%
Nickel	18%	16%	18%	5%	6%	8%	5%	3%
Lithium	19%	31%	2%	5%	1%	4%	20%	0%
Copper	17%	27%	7%	8%	3%	5%	22%	2%
Cobalt	28%	12%	4%	5%	1%	6%	1%	16%

Figure 12 | Ownership rates by investor origin for cobalt, copper, lithium, nickel and rare earths (SUERF¹¹)

Finally, mitigation strategies such as **substitution, recycling, and stockpiling** remain **insufficient in scale or effectiveness to fully address supply vulnerabilities**.

These challenges are compounded by the inherent complexity of global Raw Materials value chains, where dependencies are often indirect and difficult to manage and have increasingly become a focus of economic foreign policy, but also, to a growing extent, a weapon in the ‘competition between systems’. Overall, the EU’s challenge is not only to secure access to raw materials, but to navigate and manage a highly complex and interdependent global system in which full autonomy remains difficult to achieve without a clear roadmap how to position the EU in the context of competing powers.

Policy Making and Communication

The policy trajectory leading to the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) reflects a broad and evolving set of initiatives developed over more than 17 years. These include the Raw Materials Initiative and the Raw Materials Supply Group (2008), the European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials and the establishment of EIT Raw Materials (2012–2014), the integration of raw

¹¹ SUERF (2024), [Capital in the Twenty-First Century: Who owns the capital of firms producing critical raw materials?](#), Policy Brief n. 944.

materials as a societal challenge under Horizon 2020 (2013), the Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials and the launch of the European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA) and EU Taxonomy (2020), culminating in the adoption of the CRMA in 2024.

While this sequence has contributed to raising awareness and fostering coordination across industry, academia and public authorities, it has also been characterised by a predominance of strategic frameworks, platforms and initiatives, with comparatively limited deployment of concrete operational instruments at scale. As a result, **the translation of strategic objectives into tangible supply security outcomes has remained slower and more fragmented than required by evolving geopolitical and industrial realities.**

In this respect, **international experiences**, such as the Japan Organization for Metals and Energy Security (JOGMEC), illustrate a more operational approach, **combining policy coordination with direct financial and industrial engagement through equity investments, debt guarantees, joint ventures, geological exploration and mandated stockpiling.** Notably, such an approach enabled Japan to significantly reduce its dependence on rare earths within a relatively short timeframe following the 2010 supply disruptions.

By contrast, the EU approach has so far struggled to match this level of speed and operational effectiveness. The recent decision by the European Commission to progressively secure stakes in mining projects represents an important shift. However, if the EU is **to move from a predominantly regulatory role towards a more active co-investor role**, this transition **will require a structured governance framework, adequate financial capacity and clearly defined strategic priorities**, rather than ad hoc or incremental adjustments.

The EU's governance framework also reflects its commitment to inclusive and participatory policymaking. Since its establishment under the Treaty of Rome in 1957, the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) has played a key role in representing organised civil society—employers, workers, business organisations and other stakeholders—and in bridging EU institutions with socio-economic realities. In the context of the CRMA, consultation mechanisms have ensured broad stakeholder input. However, the expansion of consultation processes beyond established institutional channels may also introduce risks of dilution of focus and delays, highlighting the need to balance inclusiveness with efficiency and timely decision-making.

All the above is the foundation for the policy and industrial recommendations developed in the next section.

Core Recommendations

Building on the analysis presented above, and acknowledging the broad series of initiatives the European Commission has been adopting in the last years to increase—either directly or indirectly—EU's strategic autonomy¹², a broad set of recommendations derived from the LEADER 2030 project are proposed. They are structured into a **set of cross-cutting priority areas, reflecting the key levers through which the European Union, Member States and industry can strengthen the resilience, sustainability and strategic autonomy** of both the rail and raw materials value chains.

These priority areas are **inherently interdependent** and should be implemented in a **coordinated manner**, ensuring **consistency between industrial, regulatory, financial and technological actions**.

1. Strengthening Value Chain Coordination, Governance and Institutional Capacity

A first priority concerns the need to move from fragmented approaches towards system-level coordination and governance across both the rail and raw materials value chains, supported by stronger institutional capacity, strategic intelligence and ecosystem-level coordination.

This includes strengthening foresight, intelligence and coordinated R&D efforts to anticipate supply risks, innovation interdependencies and deployment constraints (A.1), and building a European, SME-inclusive rail data ecosystem able to support multi-tier visibility, early warning and coordinated mitigation actions (A.3).

It also requires strengthening ecosystem-level support structures, notably cluster-based resilience support and interregional cooperation for SMEs (B.6), while improving consultation and dialogue mechanisms between institutions and industry, particularly in CRM-related supply chains (F.6, I.1, I.2).

Institutional strengthening should also include:

- Raising raw materials awareness across EU institutions and Member States, and ensuring adequate staffing and expertise within relevant Directorates-General (G.2)
- Establishing dedicated EU market intelligence capacities on CRM value chains (G.3)
- Reinforcing the role of the European Economic and Social Committee in shaping balanced policy approaches (G.1)
- Creating a European state-supported investment and procurement organisation for raw materials, modelled on JOGMEC, to strengthen Europe's collective capacity to act in global markets (G.4).

2. Unlocking Investment, Financing and De-risking Mechanisms

A second priority concerns the mobilisation of adequate financial instruments to support resilience, industrial transformation and strategic autonomy across both value chains.

For the Rail industrial ecosystem, targeted support is needed to enable SMEs to invest in resilience technologies and stockpiling strategies (B.4, B.5), while Circularity and substitution solutions require public support to scale business models, pilots and industrial deployment (C.2, D.6).

For the Raw materials value chain, the financing challenge is even more structural. It requires:

¹² They are listed in the Table 1 of the "LEADER 2030 Final intelligence analysis and recommendations to deliver Europe's Rail in 2030", p. 27-31. The document can be accessed through the link and QR code at the end of this Brief.

- Improving access to finance for mining and processing projects, including support for early-stage developers (F.2)
- Introducing price stabilisation and protection mechanisms to mitigate market volatility and enable long-term investments (F.3)
- Expanding the use of political risk insurance instruments for operations in third countries (F.4)
- ensuring funding for external infrastructure and diversification projects, including through initiatives such as Global Gateway (H.3)
- Improving the attractiveness and timeliness of support for CRMA Strategic Projects, including financing, offtake facilitation and earlier-stage support (I.2, I.5, I.6)
- Mobilising both public and private capital, including through the Capital Markets Union and strategic industrial instruments such as IPCEIs (K.2, K.5).

3. Simplifying Regulation and Ensuring a Competitive Framework

A third priority focuses on improving framework conditions and reducing the regulatory frictions that limit industrial competitiveness, circularity and supply diversification.

For both the Rail and Raw Materials value chains, this requires reducing administrative burdens and regulatory fragmentation (F.1), while streamlining qualification, certification and approval procedures for material substitution and alternative materials (D.2, D.5).

At the same time, new regulatory requirements should remain proportionate, predictable and accompanied by sufficient transition periods, especially where standards and compliance obligations cascade through complex supply chains (C.3).

At Raw materials level, specific improvements are needed to:

- Review and adapt the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), ensuring realistic benchmarks, flexible milestones and alignment with industrial capacities (H.2)
- Ensure a level playing field globally, considering the strategic policies adopted by competing economies (H.1)
- Simplify and improve the functioning of CRMA Strategic Projects, reducing complexity and enhancing predictability (I.3, I.4).

More broadly, horizontal regulatory frameworks should also be improved to support industrial resilience and competitiveness, including through adjustments to REACH, CBAM and the Net Zero Industry Act (J.1, J.2, J.3), while better addressing the trade-offs between environmental protection and strategic autonomy in relation to mining activities and land use (J.4).

4. Scaling Circularity, Innovation and Industrial Capacity

A fourth priority concerns accelerating circularity, innovation and industrial capacity development to reduce dependencies and strengthen European competitiveness.

For the Rail sector, this includes strengthening regional circular ecosystems and industrial symbiosis (C.1), scaling recycling technologies and business models (C.2), enabling the industrial uptake of secondary materials through standards, traceability and supplier support (C.3), integrating eco-design and circularity principles across the value chain (C.4), fostering circular procurement with recycled-content and Life-Cycle Cost logic (C.5), and developing professional guidance for recyclers (C.6).

At the same time, innovation efforts should focus on developing CRM-free or CRM-reduced components (D.3), extending product lifetimes through modular and upgradeable design (D.4), accelerating the uptake of Advanced Materials and composite solutions (D.6, D.7), and deploying

more agile production pathways such as additive manufacturing, remanufacturing and Manufacturing-as-a-Service (D.8).

For the Raw Materials ecosystem, this priority also translates into maintaining and expanding European processing and refining capacity in the midstream segment (K.6), and supporting R&D across the full value chain with stronger focus on market uptake and technological leadership (K.3, K.4).

5. Enhancing Supply Chain Resilience and Strategic Logistics

A fifth priority addresses the internal capabilities that companies—especially SMEs—need in order to anticipate disruptions, respond effectively and remain competitive.

This includes structuring supply chain strategy and governance in line with business priorities (B.1), formalising supply chain risk management and contingency planning (B.2), and investing in real-time visibility technologies, data governance and digital integration across the chain (B.3).

It also requires promoting a broader value-chain preparedness model that extends beyond Tier-1 visibility and addresses hidden vulnerabilities across lower tiers (A.2), and establishing internal 'Resilience Teams' to connect R&I, engineering, industrialisation and procurement around design-for-resilience choices (D.1).

At system level, the continuity of critical industrial supplies along EU Rail Corridors must be safeguarded through improved prioritisation, corridor governance, monitoring and decision-making, including the implications of crisis-response frameworks (E.1).

6. Aligning Market Design, Procurement and Industrial Incentives

A sixth, cross-cutting priority concerns the need to better align market incentives, procurement practices and industrial policies with resilience and strategic autonomy objectives.

Current market dynamics—often focused on lowest-cost sourcing—limit the uptake of more secure, sustainable or European-based solutions. Addressing this requires stronger use of value-based procurement approaches, including Life Cycle Costing, MEAT principles, recycled-content incentives and longer-lifetime criteria (C.3, C.5, D.4).

It also requires better alignment between private-sector incentives and EU strategic objectives in international CRM partnerships and industrial projects (I.1, I.2), as well as broader productivity and technology-diffusion gains that help firms compete on more than purchase price alone (K.1).

7. Strengthening the Broader Macroeconomic and Strategic Conditions for European Autonomy

A seventh priority concerns the broader macroeconomic and strategic conditions needed to make resilience and autonomy economically sustainable over time.

This includes reducing electricity costs for Energy-Intensive Industries, which remain a major obstacle to European processing and refining capacity (F.5), and improving productivity, innovation diffusion and foreign direct investment conditions across the EU economy (K.1).

It also requires stronger mobilisation of private savings and institutional capital for industrial growth (K.2), and the use of strategic instruments—such as IPCEIs for rare earths mining and processing—where these can help close critical gaps in Europe's autonomy and competitiveness (K.5).

Lastly, it also requires to continue to pursue the strategy of acquiring direct ownership of strategic raw materials through mine ownership; to secure a right of first refusal or preemptive purchase

right for the raw materials extracted in strategic projects under the CRMA; to give the recommendations of the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC)—a EU Institution bringing the technical advice of social and industrial stakeholders—in public consultations on Acts and Directives greater weight.

(A) To foster Value chain's resilience

A.1 - POLICY / INDUSTRY: Continue and consolidate Europe's Rail coordinated R&D and intelligence efforts

A.2 - INDUSTRY / POLICY: Foster a value chain preparedness model

A.3 - POLICY / INDUSTRY: Foster a European, SME-inclusive Rail data ecosystem

(B) To foster Companies' internal resilience

B.1 – INDUSTRY: Structure supply chain strategy and governance

B.2 – INDUSTRY: Structure supply chain risk and resilience strategies

B.3 – INDUSTRY: Invest in real-time supply visibility technologies

B.4 – POLICY (INDUSTRIAL, REGIONAL): Support SMEs to access technologies for resilience

B.5 – POLICY (INDUSTRIAL, FINANCIAL, COMPETITION): Support stockpiling measures for SMEs

B.6 – POLICY (INDUSTRIAL, REGIONAL): Strengthen Cluster policies for resilience support

(C) To increase Critical Raw Materials availability

Circularity of materials

C.1 – POLICY (REGIONAL, ENVIRONMENTAL, INDUSTRIAL): Strengthen Regions as active nodes of resilient and sustainable value chains

C.2 – POLICY (RESEARCH, INDUSTRIAL, ENVIRONMENTAL): Support R&D and business models to boost recycling

C.3 – POLICY / INDUSTRY: Enable industrial uptake of secondary materials through standards, traceability and supply chain support

C.4 – INDUSTRY: Introduce Eco-design and Circularity in all stages of the value chain

C.5 – INDUSTRY: Foster Circularity in procurements

C.6 – INDUSTRY: Develop professional guidance for recyclers

(D) To reduce dependence on Critical Raw Materials

Alternative design

D.1 – INDUSTRY: Establish 'Resilience Teams' within companies

D.2 – POLICY / INDUSTRY: Introduce more flexibility in materials substitutions

D.3 – POLICY / INDUSTRY: Investigate actions to develop CRMs-free components

D.4 – POLICY / INDUSTRY: Design for extended lifetime of components

Alternative materials

D.5 – POLICY: Simplify and accelerate usage of alternative materials

D.6 – POLICY / INDUSTRY: Foster substitution with Advanced Materials

D.7 - INDUSTRY: Foster substitution with Composites

Alternative production

D.8 - INDUSTRY: Adopt agile production pathways to increase resilience

(E) To secure intra-EU freight logistics

E.1 – POLICY: Ensure regular flows of critical industrial supplies along EU Rail Corridors

AIMED AT SUPPORTING THE RAW MATERIALS VALUE CHAIN DIRECTLY

(F) Improve framework conditions of the EU Single Market for Energy-Intensive Industries

F.1 - POLICY: Reducing bureaucracy and regulatory burdens

F.2 - POLICY: Financing

F.3 - POLICY: Establishing new value chains, compensating for know-how deficits, price protection

F.4 - POLICY: Deployment of political risk insurance

F.5 - POLICY: Reducing electricity costs

F.6 - POLICY: Enhancing EU–Private sector dialogue for effective CRM de-risking

(G) Strengthen existing and building adequate new institutional capacity

G.1 - POLICY: Strengthen European Economic and Social Committee

G.2 - POLICY: Raise Raw Materials awareness and building institutional capacity

G.3 - POLICY: Set up EU Market Intelligence capacities

G.4 - POLICY: Set up State-supported investment and procurement organisation

(H) Review the Critical Raw Materials Act

H.1 - POLICY: Ensure a level playing field at global level

H.2 - POLICY: Determine realistic benchmarks

H.3 - POLICY: Funding for infrastructure in external diversification

(I) Improve support mechanisms for European companies

I.1 - POLICY: Align Private sector interests with the EU'S ambitions for Strategic Raw Materials Partnerships

I.2 - POLICY: Incentivise the Private sector

I.3 - POLICY: Decrease regulative risk potential regarding the implementation of the CRMA Strategic Projects

I.4 - POLICY: Simplify CRMA Strategic Projects application

I.5 - POLICY: Incentivise Strategic Projects owners

I.6 - POLICY: Extend CRMA Strategic Projects support to earlier-stage projects

(J) Amend Regulations and better balance the interest of strategic mining and private investments in projects in Europe

J.1 - POLICY: Amend REACH

J.2 - POLICY: Amend the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)

J.3 - POLICY: Amend the Net Zero Industry Act

J.4 - POLICY: Better balance of strategic mining projects in Europe with the EU's supposed attempts to expand Nature Protected Areas

(K) Improve Macro Indicators

K.1 - POLICY: Raise productivity and Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) in the EU

K.2 - POLICY: Stimulate private investments

K.3 - POLICY: Stimulate R&D for technological leadership

K.4 - POLICY: Prioritise funding R&D close to market uptake

K.5 – POLICY: IPCEI for Rare Earths Mining and Processing?

K.6 - POLICY: Encourage the Private sector to more investments in the Midstream segment

Taken together, these priority areas highlight the need for a comprehensive and coordinated European strategy, addressing simultaneously governance, financing, regulation, innovation, logistics and market design.

Only through such an integrated approach can the EU ensure that its industrial transformation—across Rail, Clean Technologies, Defence and beyond—remains both achievable and sustainable in an increasingly constrained and competitive global environment.

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